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Teaching Speaking in Senior High School Using Gallery Walk

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Abstract: Speaking is defined as a reflection of the students' ability to communicate in English. Compared to the other language skills, speaking is considered to be more difficult because it occurs in real time, and when we speak we cannot edit and revise what we want to say, as we can do in writing. Speaking skill was considered as a difficult skill to be maintained; therefore, an extensive practice is required to perform. However, students tend to be silent in the classroom since they lack of self-confidence. Students need more practice, so that they could learn to express their feeling, thought, idea, emotion and intention, whereas, teachers should create a good situation in teaching learning process in the classroom. Gallery walk is one of the most learner centered activities which provides good situation in teaching learning process. It is a presentation method in which individual learners or groups displayed their products, and they walked around the room viewing others' work. The purpose of this paper is to describe gallery walk technique to teach speaking in Senior High School. This technique seems to be suitable to provide fresh atmosphere in teaching English especially in Speaking.

Keywords: *Teaching Speaking, Gallery Walk*

INTRODUCTION

Many students are observed to feel that speaking English is harder than reading, writing and listening. Unlike reading or writing, speaking happens in real time. The person whom we are talking to is usually waiting for us to speak right then. When

speaking, editing and revising what to say cannot be done as we can do in writing. An extensive practice is required to help them speaking English as a foreign language. However, it is not such an easy way to maintain teaching speaking to give students practice. It is caused by the fact that students tend to be silent in the classroom and they lack of self-confidence. Students do need more practice since through practice they could learn to express their feeling, thought, idea, intention or even emotion. Besides teachers should be able to realize their problem in speaking and then create a good atmosphere in the process of teaching and learning for speaking in the classroom. One of the most learner centered activities which provides good situations in teaching and learning process is by using gallery walk.

Some researches on teaching English by using gallery walk have been conducted and proven to be effective. Anwar (2015) found that her students' speaking skill in can be enhanced by gallery walk technique in teaching learning process. Another research conducted by Mulyani (2014) on students of junior high school concludes that the students' achievement of writing announcement text who were taught by using gallery walk technique was higher or better than those who were taught by using conventional method. Referring to the previous studies, similarly the writer considers gallery walk technique seems also to increase the achievement of speaking, because it is proven to be able to enhance students' speaking skill.

Speaking is activity in producing verbal utterances to convey meaning. Teaching speaking means to prepare students with opportunities to produce verbal utterances so that they are able to communicate. Gallery walk is an active teaching strategy that gets students out of their seats and moving around the classroom to different learning stations that display artifacts related to the class activities (Edel, 2015). Teaching speaking in senior high school using gallery walk means teacher design learning activities to facilitate students to practice expressing their feeling, thought, idea, intention or even emotion by using a technique where senior high school students get out of their chairs and move around the classroom to go to learning stations displayed on the walls.

Since students are observed to get difficulty in speaking because of lack of self-confidence and motivation, creating situations of teaching learning process is badly needed. From the reason above, this paper tries to contribute to overcome the problem of teaching speaking by creating a good situation in which enhances the students' speaking ability by using gallery walk technique. Gallery walk is one of the most versatile learner centered activities. It connects learners to each other and learners to the training topic in a number of interesting and interactive ways (Bowman, 2005). By using it is hoped the students are able to involve the emotional power to find new knowledge and motivate themselves to be active to improve their self-confidence to speak. To clarify the problem that is going to be analyzed, statement of the problem is what is teaching speaking in senior high school using gallery walk like.

Based on the statement above, the objective of this paper is to describe teaching speaking in senior high school using gallery walk. After this study has been completed, there will be benefits. Theoretically this study can contribute for similar problem in the classroom. Practically, it can be the guidance for teacher as well as student. For researcher, it can be used as reference to develop the study. For students, it enables them to improve their speaking skill and to make students easier to explore their speaking skill by using gallery walk technique. And for English teacher, they will have valuable experience in using new technique to find out the best and effective technique in developing students' speaking skill.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Teaching Speaking

Teaching speaking is activities to promote speaking in English as a foreign language. It means that teaching speaking is to provide students with opportunities to practice in producing the English speech sounds and sound pattern, using word and sentence stress, intonation patterns and the rhythm of the second language, selecting appropriate words and sentences according to the proper social setting, audience, situation, and subject matter, organizing their thought in a meaningful and logical

sequence, using language as a means of expressing values and judgments, and using the language quickly and confidently with few unnatural pauses, which is called as fluency. Teaching speaking is very important part in foreign language learning. The ability to communicate in foreign language clearly and efficiently contributes to the success of the learner in school as well as later in real life. Therefore it is essential that language teachers pay a great attention for teaching speaking.

The goal of teaching speaking should be providing students with strategies to improve their communication outside the classroom. Lackman (2010) states that rather than just have students ‘speak’ in the classroom we should be teaching students specific speaking skills, known as sub-skills or micro skills. Since conversation outside the class are bound to be better learning experiences that those inside the class, rather than trying to duplicate real-world conversation in the classroom. We should be teaching students skills they are not likely to learn outside the classroom. By raising of awareness of speaking sub-skills and providing classroom practice with them, we will be providing students with strategies to improve their communication outside the classroom, which is, or should be the ultimate goal.

What to teach in speaking class? Teachers should teach students speaking sub-skills and by providing practice in different types or function of speaking. The main speaking sub-skills are fluency, accuracy, and appropriacy (Lackman, 2010). Fluency deals with the ease or the smoothness of speaking, accuracy covers the correct use of pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary. And appropriateness deals with the use different language in different situation, it relates to time, place, turn taking, socio-cultural, and politeness. While the functions of speaking, as stated by Richard (2008), are as interaction, transaction, and performance.

2. Gallery Walk

What is gallery walk? Bowman (2005) considers gallery walk as one of the most versatile learner centered activities. It has been called by a lot of names and has many variations. We can use it as an information rich opening (connection), closing

(celebration), or review activity. The gallery walk connects learners to each other and learner to the teaching topic in a number of interesting and interactive ways. Hosseinali (2014) states that gallery walk is a discussion technique that gets students out of their chairs and into a mode of active engagement. For students it's a chance to share thoughts in a more intimate, supportive setting rather than a larger, anonymous class. For instructors, it's a chance to gauge the depth of student understanding of particular concepts and to challenge misconceptions.

Gallery walk is a discussion technique for active engagement. Gallery walk is a cooperative learning strategy in which the instructor devises several questions/problem at a different table or at different place on the wall- hence the name 'gallery'. Students form groups and each group moves from question to question- hence the name 'walk'. After writing the group's response to the first question, the group rotates to the next position, adding to what is already there. At the last question it is the group responsibility to summarize and report to the class. Hosseinali (2014) states that gallery walk get student out of their chairs and actively involves them in synthesizing important concepts, in consensus building, in writing, and in public speaking. In gallery walk teams rotate around the classroom, composing answers to questions as well as reflecting upon the answers given by other groups. Questions are posted on charts or just a piece of paper located at different parts of the classroom. Each chart or station has its own question that relate to an important class concept. This technique closes with an oral presentation in which each group synthesizes comments to a particular question.

Why gallery walk is used? It promotes high order thinking, oral or written presentation skills, and team building. It is flexible and has many benefits. Gallery walk can be organized for a simple fifteen minutes' ice breaker or for a week long project involving oral and written reports. This technique encourages students to speak and write rather than just hearing it from the teacher. Besides dealing with a variety of cognitive skills which involve analysis, evaluation, and synthesis, gallery walk has the additional advantage of promoting cooperation, listening skills, and team building.

How to use gallery walk? Student teams rotate between posted charts. In gallery walk student teams rotate to provide bulleted answers to questions posted on charts arranged around the classroom. After three to five minutes at a chart or "station" the team rotates to the next question. Gallery walk works best with open ended questions, that is, when a problem, concept, issue, or debate can be analyzed from several different perspectives. In this section teacher should find a variety of instructional resources such as preparing students for this technique, a step by step guide for using gallery walk, evaluation rubrics, and challenges in implementing the technique.

METHODOLOGY

This study was classroom action research (CAR) study. Burns (2010) states that action research is related to the idea of reflective practice and the teacher as a researcher. It involves taking a self-reflective, critical, and systematic approach to exploring our own teaching context. It also enables teachers to investigate their classrooms such as their method of teaching, students' learning, assessment used, etc. intended to improve their teaching and learning process.

This study aimed to improve students' speaking skill through gallery walk technique. The researcher observed how the teacher implemented the technique. Valid and reliable speaking test was conducted to measure the improvement of the students speaking skill. Moreover, this study was conducted at one of the state school on Kalasan, Sleman, Yogyakarta. The participants of the research are 32 students in grade X which consisted of 10 male and 12 female students. This study was conducted into two cycles; each cycle consisted of planning, action, observation and reflection. In planning, the teacher prepared the materials, made lesson plan, designed the steps in doing research, prepared list of students' names, determines teaching aids, prepared classroom observation, and determined the rubric to assess students' speaking skill. In action, the plan of classroom action research was implemented; the teacher committed to follow the plan, however the teacher still taught naturally to get accurate information. In observing, camera was used to record so that the whole process could be observed. Finally,

reflection would be conducted whether the technique had fulfilled the aim of the research or not.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A basic learning of language learning is language as communication. Perhaps the most fundamental reality of language learning is that language is a tool for communication. The goal of most students learning English in schools of non-English speaking countries is to communicate with other English speakers, some are native, but probably most non-native both intra and intra-nationally and internationally. Therefore, those learners only need achievable models who are competent users of English. Today there are more multilingual English teachers who are very competent speakers of English. They can also be ideal speakers – models to provide learners with practicable and appropriate models for using English as a lingua franca.

The functions on speaking in human interaction are classified into useful distinction between the interactional function of speaking, in which it serves to establish and maintain social relations, and the transactional functions, which focus on the exchange of information. Richard (2008) expands the classification into *talk as interaction*, *talk as transaction*, and *talk as performance*. Each of these speech activities is quite different in terms of form and function and also requires different teaching approaches. The followings are explanation of each classification.

The first classification is talk as interaction. It refers to what we usually mean by conversation. It describes interaction that serves mainly a social function. Take for example, when people meet, they exchange greetings, take part in small talk, tell a story about recent experience, and so on because they wish to be friendly and establish a comfortable zone of interaction with others. The focus is more on the speakers and how they wish to present themselves to each other than on the message. In other word it reflects speaker's identity. The exchanges may be either casual or formal depending on the situation. It reflects degrees of politeness, uses conversational register, and is jointly constructed.

Mastering the skill of talk as interaction seems to be difficult and students may not prioritize it. But, students who do need such skills sometimes feel difficult to deal with and feel a loss for words when they find themselves in situations that require talk for interaction. They get difficulty in presenting a good image of themselves and then they sometimes avoid situations that demand this kind of talk. To deal with this difficult situation, at the beginning, learners may depend on familiar topics. They also need practice in introducing new topics into conversation. They should practice nominating topics which are prepared to speak about. They should practice predicting question for a large number of topics, they should be taught elicitation devices to get topic clarification (Hatch in Richard, 2008). For instance, they should practice saying “huh”, “pardon me”, “excuse me, I didn’t understand”, etc. and echoing parts of sentences they do not understand in order to get it recycled again.

The second classification of speaking is talk as transaction. It refers to situation in which the focus is on what is said or done. In other word we could say that the purpose of speaking is to get things done. The central focus is on the message and making oneself understand clearly and accurately, rather than on the people who involve in speaking and on how they interact socially with each other. In the transactions, talk is connected with other activities. The examples of talk as transaction are: classroom group discussion and problem solving activities, a class activity during which students design a poster, discussing sightseeing plans with a hotel clerk or tour guide, making a telephone call to get flight information, asking someone for directions on the street, buying something in a shop, ordering from a menu in a restaurant, etc.

The followings are the main features of talk as transaction. It has a primarily information focus. The main focus is on the message and not the participants. Participants employ communication strategies to make them understood. There may be frequent questions, repetitions, and negotiation. Linguistic accuracy is not always important. Some of the skills involved in using talk as transactions explaining a need or intention, describing something, making suggestion, making comparison, agreeing and disagreeing, etc.

In this classification of speaking which consider talk as transaction, Burns in Richards (2008) divides it into two types. The first type involves situations where the focus is on giving and receiving the information, and where the participants focus primarily on what is said or achieved. For example, asking someone for directions, accuracy may not be the priority as long as information is successfully communicated and understood. The second type is transactions that focus on obtaining good or services, such as checking into a hotel or ordering food in a restaurant.

The third classification of speaking that can be usefully distinguished has been called talk as performance. It refers to public speaking, that is, talk that transmits information in front of an audience, such as classroom presentations, public announcements, and speeches. According to Jones in Richards (2008) this kind of spoken texts often have identifiable generic structure and the language use is more predictable. Because of less contextual support, the speaker must include all necessary information. And meaning is important; there will be more emphasis on form and accuracy. Talk as performance tends to be in the form of monolog rather than dialog. Examples of talk as performance are giving a class report about a school trip, giving a welcoming speech, making a sales presentation, giving a lecture, etc.

What are the features of talk as performance? It focuses on both message and audience. The organization is predictable and sequencing. Both form and accuracy are important. It often considered as a monolog. Talk as performance involves some of the skill, such as using a appropriate format, presenting information in appropriate sequence, maintaining audience engagement, using correct pronunciation and grammar, creating an effect on the audience, using appropriate vocabulary, using an appropriate opening and closing.

For teaching speaking, the three classifications above need to be addressed in planning speaking activities for an English class. Firstly, it is to determine what kind of speaking skills the class will focus on. Is it all the genres described above or will some receive greater attention than others? Secondly, it is to identify teaching strategies to provide opportunities for learners to acquire each kind of talk.

Anyway it is not just an easy way to plan speaking activities since students are reluctant to speak. Harmer (2007) states that students are reluctant to speak because shy and predispose to expressing themselves in front of people especially when they are being asked to give personal information or opinions. Luckily gallery walk comes as a strategy in building encouragement. Gallery walk is a classroom-based active leaning strategy where students are encouraged to build their knowledge about a topic or content to promote higher order thinking, interaction, and cooperative learning. The students in groups move through different stations where a question is posted for them to answer and interact and share knowledge in the process.

The steps in gallery walk technique engage students to practice speaking. Students firstly are divided into small groups. The teacher posts different open-ended questions in the form of text or image related to a particular context/topic on the classroom wall with sufficient distance between them. This arrangement helps the students to walk around from one place to another to view the questions. Each student group is assigned to one question in the beginning of the activity and students in the group can discuss and write their thought, facts, or solution to the question. After a short period of time, the group moves to the next question. They can read and criticize the reflections of the previous group who answered that question or they can provide their own thoughts. This continues till the last question. When after walking in the classroom contributing to the solution of all questions, the groups return to the first question they faced. Meanwhile the teacher observes the students' participation in the activity and also gives inputs to the students.

During the process of teaching and learning, some positive atmospheres for learning speaking emerge. Students interact and synthesize the concepts. It makes learning more effective and promotes higher order thinking skills because they speak in authentic way, in a real context and topic. Students are encouraged to move around without having to sit in one place for a long time, so that it may remove boredom. Students get to know about different views of the same topic, thus improving learning opportunity. Students are encouraged to use the appropriate language and terminologies

of the subject; it means that they improve their knowledge. It improves public-speaking skills and develops team-building and listening skill among students.

CONCLUSION

Using gallery walk in teaching speaking has some advantages. It provides students to practice the functions of speaking. Students get a chance to make interaction as well as transaction talk when they exchange ideas, besides they also practice talk as performance when they report to class. In addition, it gives students practice speaking sub-skills. When they are doing gallery walk, they practice speaking meaning that their fluency, accuracy, and appropriateness improve since they have to communicate with their classmate using real context and appropriate language and terminologies.

In using gallery walk for teaching speaking, it is advisable to use some variation of the media so that students will not be bored. Gallery walk technique could also be used for teaching other skills. It is suggested that gallery walk is used in pre or post activity of teaching reading, writing or listening as an opening, connecting or brainstorming and a closing or celebration.

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